

Book Review - Economics of Education: Selected Issues to Educators

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Book Title: Economics of Education: Selected Issues to Educators

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Abstract

*Scarcity of resources required to implement curriculum at all levels of education has been felt globally; the situation has further been worsened by emergence of Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore there is need for a reform in the use of resources that have been dedicated to the education sector in order to achieve the goals of education. The book **Economics of Education: Selected issues to Educators** sets out to deal with these matters. In its six chapters; the work addresses conceptual issues related to the subject; integration between Education and human capital. The Macro-economic & Micro-economic approaches are thoroughly examined. Basic features of Economic analysis of educational intervention and importance are tackled. The notion of cost-benefit is ideally attended to. Additionally, education efficiency and financing of higher education are also well discussed. The author traces the global perspective on financing higher education, the types of financing higher education are also put into consideration where funding of higher education in Tanzania is used as case study. The section on quality education looks at rationale of providing quality education among other issues. The work is recommended as a text book for economics of education at undergraduate and post graduate levels.*

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1.0 Introduction

The advent of Covid 19 has brought about economic challenges in developed and developing countries. Therefore there is need to sustainably use resources that have been dedicated to the education sector. The introductory section of the book *Economics of Education: Selected issues to Educators* comprises of the Preface where opening remarks about the work is presented. The principal reasons that motivated the writer to come up with this work are highlighted.

2.0 Discussion

The book has six chapters; the first chapter of the book addresses conceptual issues such as: definition of key terms, relevance of economics of education, areas where economics is applied to education. The author briefly explains why education is an investment and not just consumption. On page 5, additional information about the concept of consumption is given by asserting that consumption benefits of education are non-monetary returns accruing to individuals throughout their life time. The author also shows that education as investment increases productivity of an individual throughout one's life. The chapter also provides answers as to why society needs to invest in education as argued by Boruch (2012). These include; Production of human capital, Cost effectiveness, Program planning and Creates awareness. The section is very interesting as it gives suggestions on how school dropouts can be dealt with so as to reduce wastages.

The work outlines the roles of eminent economists such as: Adam Smith, David Ricardo, John Stuart, Alfred Marshal and Henry Von Thunen in development of the field of economics of education. Education is important as it reduces human miseries, exhaustively discusses the concept of education as a product, employs education production function to highlight role of education in the society; and explains the law of demand and supply.

The second chapter unlike other works describes the integration between Education and *human capital*. The Macro-economic & Micro-economic approaches as profoundly suggested by Parter are thoroughly examined. The

concept of human capital in education, its features, theory and philosophy are also comprehensively treated.

Chapter three addresses *Economic analysis of educational* intervention its basic features and importance are tackled. The notion of cost-benefit is ideally attended to. Additionally, education efficiency and its types are evaluated; internal efficiency of education is in detail analyzed by showing its indicators and factors as shown in (pp.78-79). Besides, Economies of scale in education is addressed by showing its application and strategies to be used to achieve effective education.

Chapter four introduces the concept of *Financing of Higher Education*. Unlike other works which have similar materials, the author begins by tracing the global perspective on financing higher education; the types of financing higher education are also put into consideration. This is an added advantage to the reader as he or she is exposed to the background before handling substantive issues. The chapter further looks at policies for funding Higher Education in Tanzania; Major ways of funding education in Tanzania, challenges of financing Higher are as well put into account. In addition, challenges relating to students' loans are broadly dealt with. This is very important. Most recently there have been concerns especially in developing countries on whether governments should continue to finance higher education through loans or use grants.

The work is unique as in Chapter five it explores the types of evaluations in education, how they can be used and how to carry out evaluation in Higher Education systems. This particular section is very educative to readers would want to find out whether education is really an investment. There have been concerns that resources devoted to education should be reduced.

The sixth chapter is on *Quality education* it looks at dimensions of quality education, rationale of providing quality education, declarations on quality, major factors affecting quality education, human rights education, and the importance of measuring quality, benchmarking types, objectives; methodologies and its application in education. Countries dedicate a lot of funds to finance the education

sector in both developing and developed countries. These resources would go to waste if quality education is not provided to the citizens.

3.0 Conclusion

In its six chapters the author has ably explained how best resources can be used at various levels of education and therefore contributes to realisation of goals of education and a better world. The book is a mine of information about economics of education. The author has used clear, simple language and case studies that are clearly understood. It is recommended as a text book for economics of education at both undergraduate and post graduate levels of education.